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ЖУРНАЛ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ | JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LANDSCAPE TERMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

ANNOTATION

The article describes the comparative analysis, semantics, and phraseological combinations of landscape terms in Uzbek and English used in modern linguistics.

Key words: language, comparative, English, phraseology, combinations, tasks, culture, linguo-culturology, relationship, units, related.

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СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ЛАНДШАФТНЫХ ТЕРМИНОВ НА УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье описан сравнительный анализ, семантика и фразеологические сочетания ландшафтных терминов в узбекском и английском языках, используемых в современной лингвистике.

Ключевые слова: язык, сравнительный, английский, фразеология, сочетания, задачи, культура, лингво культурология, взаимосвязь, единицы, родственные.

USMONOVA Shahnoza

Farg'ona davlat universiteti

O'qituvchisi

LANDSHAFT ATAMALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA

АННОТАЦИЯ

Maqolada zamonaviy tilshunoslikda qo'llaniladigan o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi landshaft atamalarining qiyosiy tahlili, semantikasi va frazeologik birikmalari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: til, qiyosiy, ingliz tili, frazeologiya, birikmalar, vazifalar, madaniyat, lingvo-kulturologiya, munosabatlar, birliklar, tegishli.

Research in modern linguistics shows the relationship between the linguistic and cultural formation of phraseological unit's language and culture, because fixed expressions are more closely related to the life of people than others. They are formed on the basis of many centuries of life experience, traditions and rituals that exist today. Creating phraseological units in languages of different structures, their etymology, structure, semantics and their classification is one of the important tasks of linguistics.

Literature analysis. A number of studies on phraseological units in the world known to be linguistics. Therefore, the works of L.A. Bulakhovsky, A.V. Kunin, L.Kuliyev, K.Musaev, I.S.Stepanova, I.N. Isabekova, A.V. Urazmetova are of great importance in this regard. Z.K.Korzyukova's research shows that the most important feature of phraseological units in English linguistics is analyzed on the basis of "Anglo-Russian language" as opposite components dictionary" Kunin [1, B.14].

In his research, he pays great attention to etymology, linguistic and mental properties of expressions, as well as their classification. In Uzbek linguistics, Sh. Rahmatullaev compiled an explanatory dictionary of phraseological units. A.E. Mamatov monographed the formation factors of phraseological units in the Uzbek language. B. Reimov conducted research on phraseological units reflecting the emotional state of a person, G.E. Hakimova studied phraseological units with zoological names

M. Vafoeva studied phraseological synonyms in the Uzbek language, U. Rashidova studied somatic expressions of the Uzbek language [2, B.18].

The current state of scientific development of the current problems of linguistics, the tasks of lexicology, the general development prospects of the theory of meaning and evaluation require the search for linguistic innovations, a new look at previous problems, and at the same time include many questions that are not current. Comparatively studied in the orbit of scientific research in linguistics. Until now, the comparative study of languages (cognate and non-cognate) has been conducted mainly from the point of view of grammar.

This is completely understandable and natural, since it is easier and more accurate to compare linguistic phenomena within a certain grammar, bounded by a set of established rules, normative in its essence than in poorly defined and uncertain areas. It's better. as a vocabulary and phraseology of the language. However, at present, when certain experience has been accumulated in the comparative study of grammatical categories in different languages, the attention of linguists is increasingly focused on the lexical-phraseological aspect of the general problem of language comparison. terminology [4, B.34].

The linguistic aspect of the study of the terminological dictionary has not yet finished its problems, which makes it necessary to define the terminology as a subsystem of the general literary language from the prism of lexical-semantic and grammatical categories. The comparative study of the vocabulary materials of the Uzbek and English languages and their interaction is of great theoretical and practical importance for the further development of the comparative typological study of languages with different structures, and serves to identify new linguistic languages. facts in the languages in question.

Currently, the systematic method is increasingly used in the comparative study of languages of different grammatical systems, as well as languages of the same grammatical system, which can be considered one of the modern methods of linguistic research. At the same time, it should be noted that this method is not always equally effective in learning some levels of the language. In particular, the systematic method is not always convenient for studying the vocabulary of the language, because the systematic study of the lexical material is more difficult than the material of other layers of the language.

In modern linguistics, much attention is paid to understanding and learning the language as a system. One of the main principles of linguistics is a systematic approach to the study of language and its levels [7, B.56].

The diversity of approaches to the understanding of the systemic nature of the language, first of all, indicates the complexity, versatility, inconsistency and variability of the language system itself, its levels and units.

The features of the systematic-semantic organization of the terminological dictionary determine the specific features of the comparative-typological study of terminology as a system of reflecting the conceptual structure of a particular field of science, which is initially characterized by its system orientation and strict structural and structural organization. The specificity of the expression of a certain system of scientific concepts determines the specific characteristics of the functioning of terminology as a special semasiologically system in the dictionary. This term reflects the concepts of scientific fields.

As a result of the study and analysis of the factual material, it was shown that the following trends and laws apply in the dictionary of the English and Uzbek languages: creation of public words in the field of neutral and especially terminological vocabulary; term loan process; observation; restoration of archaisms; clarification of terminology; availability of synonyms; growth of antonymic lines; activation of adverbial and affixal word formation; increased analytical methods in term formation; self-enrichment through rethinking language, synonymy and antonyms. All this indicates the rapid evolution of the Uzbek and English terminological systems. For example, in English, one concept can be used as both a noun and a verb [6, B.78].

In linguistics, this grammatical phenomenon is called conversion, i.e. method of word formation by changing the word paradigm, which is almost never observed in the Uzbek language. The systematic study of language materials is largely related to the method of component analysis, which is based on the hypothesis that the meaning of each unit consists of semantic components, schemes or features. For example, the word uncle consists of six semantic components: 1) "a sign of a man"; 2) "parent"; 3) "relative along the horizontal line"; 4) "blood (non-blood) relative"; 5) "relative of the first generation"; 6) "older and younger than the speaker" The use of the method of component analysis in the study of lexical-semantic groups of vocabulary units (lexico-semantic field) is the most economical and therefore the most reasonable.

In fact, the semantic field itself (lexico-semantic group) is distinguished on the basis of some semantic component.

So, for example, all kinship terms are combined into one lexical-semantic field on the basis of the concept of "kinship", which is integral and leading in semantic structures. The systematic method of linguistics is sometimes accompanied by the method of synchronic comparison, which is convenient and effective in studying the system of kinship terms for languages with different and identical grammatical structures.

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